

Fiscal Policy and Inflation: Empirical Study of Pre and Post-Democratic Nigeria

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Abstract: Inflation remains a major economic issue for which how to curb or reduce it is a major macroeconomic challenge to policy makers in Nigeria. To this end, various policy measures have been adopted by various governments in Nigeria in a bid to addressing it. This study aims to empirically analyze the effectiveness of these policy interventions in curbing inflation within Nigeria from 1980 to 2020, spanning both pre and post-democratic eras. The research employed secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria annual reports and National Bureau of Statistics reports across multiple years. Analysis involved descriptive statistics, unit root tests, Johansen co-integration tests, and error correction methods to examine the data thoroughly. The study identified government spending, debt accumulation, and strong economic growth as factors mitigating inflation, whereas a higher real exchange rate contributed to its rise. This implies that any fiscal policy measure aimed at reducing rising inflation in Nigeria should properly address real exchange issues. Fiscal policy measures under various government regimes from pre- to post-democratic era in Nigeria were considered. Also, a comparison of various government regimes were made between pre- democratic era (1980-1999) and post- democratic era (1999-2020).

Keywords: Government debt stock, Government expenditure, Fiscal policy, Inflation, Real exchange rate, Real growth of the economy.

Introduction

Various pre and post-democratic government regimes in Nigeria have made controlling inflation one of their priorities by using various fiscal policy measures. Fiscal policy measures encompass a range of government actions crafted to shape both the size and distribution of revenue and spending, all aimed at fostering internal and external economic equilibrium and fostering sustainable development (Okonjo-Iweala and Osafo-Kwaako, 2007). Fiscal policies play important roles in the economy by influencing the macro-economic performance thus increasing economic activity and achieving price stability. Such fiscal policy measures include public spending and taxation. Taxation and government spending serve as the cornerstone instruments of fiscal policy, but in certain regions, grants and aid also play substantial roles as complementary tools within the fiscal framework.

Just like a driver needs a steering wheel to navigate, no nation can achieve smooth economic stability without fiscal policy, the government's tool for guiding growth and controlling what's produced and consumed. (Tule and Alade, 2017). Fiscal policy, the conductor of the economic orchestra, uses tax and spending instruments to harmonize revenue and expenditure for economic stability.

Because of the cosmopolitan nature of Nigeria, limited options and an immature economic system characterize the prevailing scarcity and developmental stage of the economy, the shallowness of its economy, fast results, public and electoral acceptance, being challenging to pre and post-democratic Nigeria, most regimes prefer and apply easier instruments that yield faster results. These fiscal policies however are interrelated and as such they influence aggregate demand; they also generate inflation. Nigeria like other developing countries does apply discretionary fiscal policy. This is as a result of its institutional weakness and financial resource constraints. As such, like every other developing country facing these challenges do not adopt the countercyclical fiscal policy (Surjaningsih, Utari and Trisnanto, 2012). However public expectations regarding governments' ability to pay maturing debt obligations create inflation. Like a ship tethered to a stormy sea, Nigeria's fiscal policy is heavily swayed by the volatile waves of oil prices. This dependence on oil, accounting for 3 out of 4 dollars in government revenue, creates a boom-and-bust cycle that can be challenging to manage.

Nigeria's economy ranked among the most volatile in the world for the period 1960 to 2000 (World Bank, 2003). Fluctuations in public expenditure re- flected both the over-

reliance on oil earnings and weak fiscal discipline by previous governments (Barnett and Ossowski, 2002). The costs of such macroeconomic volatility were significant for Nigeria. Nigeria's economy has been on a boom-bust rollercoaster since 1970, mirroring the ups and downs of oil prices. Revenue and spending have gone wild, both increasing but also swinging dramatically whenever oil prices spiked like they did in 1979-82, 1991-92, and 2000-2002. Unfortunately, the good times don't last forever. When oil prices fall, government spending often gets slammed on the brakes, albeit sometimes with a delay. This boom-and-bust approach ripples through the whole economy, creating instability and disruption.

Two important economic targets can be highlighted during pre and post-colonial Nigeria period: structural adjustment programme (SAP) targeted at faster economic growth, as a foundation for development, and secondly the economic stabilization. Various regimes in Nigeria have often applied the recommendations of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) which have had mixed effects – opening of the economy which has led to dwindling economic growth, increasing unemployment, decreasing productivity, worsening price stability (Igwe, Edeh & Ukpere, 2012; Otto and Ukpere, 2015; Egbulonu and Wobilor, 2016; Abubakar, 2016).

Vast literatures showcase the connection between government spending and inflation as intricate, with various studies painting diverse pictures. While some see a clear link, others struggle to find consistent evidence. It's a complex tango, with many factors influencing the dance. The 2008 global crises brought to fore the contradictory effect of expansionary policies on economic growth that was applied then. However, the Fiscal Theory of the Price Level (FTPL) has been the major theory that shows inflation as being the achievement of stable economic growth which hinges not just on external factors, but also on a well-calibrated fiscal policy. It acts as a crucial lever, shaping the landscape for sustainable and healthy expansion (Afonso, 2002; Christiano and Fitzgerald, 2000; Sims, 1994; Asandului, Lupu, Maha and Viorică, 2021). The prevailing focus in existing literature has predominantly centered on the linear dynamics characterizing the connection between fiscal policy, economic growth, and inflation. However, recent scholarly attention has shifted towards a comparative analysis of different fiscal regimes, particularly examining the distinctions between pre- and post-democratic eras in Nigeria. This emerging perspective offers a nuanced understanding of how fiscal policies have evolved within distinct political contexts, shedding light on the multifaceted

interplay between governance structures, economic performance, and inflationary trends. Venturing beyond oversimplified models, we delved into the nuanced exploration of potential linear connections between fiscal policy and inflation, contextualized within the distinctive timeframe spanning from 1981 to 2020 as general and for various government regimes. Prior studies exploring the link between public spending, debt, exchange rates, and inflation in Nigeria primarily focused on single government regimes. Recognizing this gap, our study takes a novel approach, analyzing these relationships across multiple regimes to capture potential variations. This gap may be because these relationships is of a linear nature taking a coup from the endogenous growth model (Igwe, Edeh and Ukpere, 2012; Eggoh and Khan, 2014; Egbulonu and Wobilor, 2016).

In computing the fiscal policy effects on inflation in Nigeria, we utilize an external measure to gauge the government's expenditure and exchange rate stance, which is proposed by Igwe, Edeh and Ukpere, (2012); and Egbulonu and Wobilor, (2016); Our novelty element of this paper is the independent analysis of each government regime pre and post-democracy and the data used which extended to 2020. Each of these governments inherits part of the last

government's fiscal policy. The fiscal policy effects on inflation are estimated by using a pooled mean. By this methodology we analyse the relationship as it is suitable for computing and comparing various government performances.

Our research hypothesis is that fiscal policy has had a great effect on inflation in Nigeria under various government regimes. Once the research hypothesis is validated, we will outline the specific results and compare various government regimes fiscal policy impact on inflation. This paper has next section as review of existing literatures on the topic, followed by description of data and the methodology used. Section four presents the findings of the analysis alongside their corresponding discussion. The final section offers conclusions drawn from the study and provides recommendations.

Theoretical and Empirical Literature

A number of researches have been carried out regarding effects of fiscal policy on macro-economic stabilization. Accordingly, these researchers explained fiscal policy as the use of taxes and expenditure by government to monitor, influence and direct its economy (Reem, 2009; Medee and Nenbee, 2011; Agu, Okwor, Ugwunta and Idike (2015). Governments aren't lone wolves when it comes to steering the economy. They often

tag-team with fiscal and monetary policies, working together to achieve economic goals like full employment, stable prices, and robust growth. John Meynard Keynes theories of fiscal policy remain the theory unto which fiscal policy is anchored. The theory linking fiscal policy to productivity is intriguing, but studies evaluating its effectiveness often disagree, suggesting factors beyond taxes and spending may play a bigger role.

Fiscal policy has been used by policy makers to stabilise the economy by its effect on aggregate demand. Policy makers employ fiscal policy as a tool to foster sustainable and robust economic growth while simultaneously aiming to keep inflation rates low and stable. Consequently, the correlation between inflation and economic growth remains a topic of fervent debate. Notably, several influential studies have indicated that inflation exerts a detrimental impact on economic growth. This underscores the importance for macroeconomic policies to prioritize the attainment of a low inflationary environment (Barro, 1991; Bruno and Easterly, 1996; Fischer, 1983, 1993; Ozurumba, 2012; Asandului, Lupu, Maha and Viorică, 2021). Previous research exploring a positive relationship between fiscal policy and inflation in Nigeria might have overlooked the nuances

of these dynamics, especially their variation under different political systems (Ezeabasilli, Mojekwu and Herbert, 2012; Hamantha, 2012; Nwaoha, 2012; Egbulonu and Wobilor, 2016). In each of these studies, the scholars agreed that there is existence of a positive relationship between fiscal policy and inflation. However, the difference is that while Egbulonu and Wobilor found a significant positive relationship, others (Ezeabasilli, Mojekwu and Herbert, 2012; Hamantha, 2012; Nwaoha, 2012) confirmed the existence of a less significant but positive relationship. Researchers such as Jeevan (2008); Magazzino (2011); Ammama, Khalid and Muhammad (2011); Medee and Nenbee (2012); Olayungbo (2013); Tai-Nguyen (2014) in their studies, conducted beyond Nigeria, have consistently identified a positive correlation between fiscal policy and inflation. Also, Ozurumba (2012) using 1970-2009 data investigated the causal link between inflation and fiscal deficits in Nigeria. The study validated a substantial negative correlation between inflation and the growth of fiscal deficits.

Some studies have been carried out in Pakistan (Ammama, Khalid and Muhammad, 2011; Abdul Qadir, 2012; Gbulam, 2014). In contrast, Ammama, Khalid & Muhammad employed cointegration methods to explore the influence of fiscal deficits on inflation. Their research

affirmed a robust positive association between fiscal policy deficits and inflation. Additionally, Gbulam examined the impacts of various fiscal policy instruments on inflation within the Pakistani economy. Their findings revealed that both direct and indirect tax increases contribute to inflationary pressures in Pakistan. Furthermore, Abdul Quadir investigated the relationship between tax revenue and inflation in Pakistan, concluding that inflation and taxes are positively correlated, implying that any alteration in inflation levels leads to corresponding changes in taxes.

Furthermore, the research carried out in Indonesia by Surjaningsih, Utari & Trisnanto (2012) found government spending to be effective during recession in spurring economic growth. Accordingly increased government spending decreases inflation while increased taxation increased inflation.

Methodology

Data sources and description

To conduct this empirical study, fiscal policy variables were extracted from various editions of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) publications. Specifically, time series data covering real gross domestic product (GDP), inflation rate, government expenditure, government total debt stock, and real exchange

rate were retrieved from the 2020 CBN Statistical Bulletin.

Model specification

We will modify the model specified by Medee & Nenbee (2012) and Egbulonu & Wobilor (2016). The model will explore the effect of fiscal policy on inflation. The assumption here is that in the post-democratic of Nigeria, the succeeding regimes in their first administrative years inherit fiscal policy plan of the outgoing government. This is prior to their remaining three years that complete the four-year tenure cycle. To this end, we adopted government total debt stock, government total expenditure, real exchange rate and growth rate of gross domestic product as a control variable.

Adopting Medee & Nenbee (2012) and Egbulonu & Wobilor (2016) models specification, we specify the following multi regression equation model;

$$INF = f(GEXP + GDST + REXR + Ygt) \quad (1)$$

Linearly, the functional relationship is thus:

$$INF = a_0 + a_1GEXP + a_2GDST + a_3REXR + a_4Ygt + \mu \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where,

INF = Inflation rate

GEXP = Total government expenditure

GDST = Total government debt stock

REXR = Real exchange rate

Ygt = Growth rate of real gross domestic product, defined by

$$Ygt = \frac{RGDP_{current\ year} - RGDP_{previous\ year}}{RGDP_{previous\ year}} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

μ = White noise error term

Expressing (2) into log-linear form,

$$\log INF = a_0 + a_1 \log GEXP + a_2 \log GDST + a_3 \log REXR + a_4 \log Ygt + \mu \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

$$\Delta INF_t = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p a_{1i} \Delta \ln GEXP_t - 1 + \sum_{i=1}^q a_{2i} \Delta \ln GDST_t - 1 +$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^q a_{3i} \Delta \ln REXR_t - 1 + \lambda ECM_t - 1 + \mu t \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Empirical results and discussion

Unit root and co-integration test results

Table 1 presents the results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, confirming the stationarity of the variables, and the Johansen cointegration test, indicating the presence of cointegration among the variables used in the model. Table 2 further demonstrates the existence of three cointegrating equations based on the maximum eigenvalue and trace statistics.

Table 1 ADF Results of unit root Test on yearly data on variables with Trend 1980-2020s

Variable	Level	1 st Diff.	Prob.	Integration Order	Critical Value of Stat.
GOVEXP	2.995298	-6.350860	0.0000	I(I)	-2.935001
GDST	2.324906	-4.481256	0.0009	I(I)	-2.935001
REXR	2.061879	-5.593156	0.0007	I(I)	-2.941145
Ygt	2.936942	-8.415462	0.0000	I(I)	-2.936942
INF	3.252224	-6.267357	0.0000	I(I)	-2.936942

Source: Researchers computation using E-View 9

Table 2 Result of Johansen Cointegration Test for Model

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.861997	124.1745	69.81889	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.606588	60.79904	47.85613	0.0019
At most 2 *	0.413288	30.94627	29.79707	0.0367
At most 3	0.328232	13.88319	15.49471	0.0862
At most 4	0.035366	1.152222	3.841466	0.2831
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistics	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.861997	63.37542	33.87687	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.606588	29.85277	27.58434	0.0251
At most 2	0.413288	17.06308	21.13162	0.1690
At most 3	0.328232	12.73097	14.26460	0.0861
At most 4	0.035366	1.152222	3.841466	0.2831

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values
Source: Researchers computation using E-View 9

Having confirmed the stationarity of the variables via the ADF test, the next is to confirm whether the variables are co-integrated or not. A co-integration among the variables; INF (Inflation), GEXP (Government expenditure), GDST (Government debt stock), REXR (Real exchange rate) and Ygt (Growth rate of

gross domestic product) shows a long run relationship among the variables. Table 2 above shows the Johansen co-integration analysis, having three co-integrating equations at 5% level of significance. Given these three co-integrating equations, the model satisfies the requirement for fitting in an error correction.

Error correction mechanism

Table 3 Parsimonious Error Correction Mechanism

Variables	Coefficient	t-Statistics	Probability
C	2.471932	0.815859	0.4212
D(LOG(GOVEXP)-1)	-15.40578	-1.964815	0.0591
D(LOG(GTDS)-1)	-2.347850	-0.256407	0.7994
D((REXR)-1)	11.07813	2.719825	0.0109
D((YGT)-1)	-1.692959	-3.329706	0.0024
ECM(-1)	-0.245768	-1.210482	0.2359
R ²	0.480382	Durbin Watson Stat.	2.073808
Adjusted R-Squared	0.390792		
F-Statistic	5.362040	Prob (F-Satistic)	0.001308

Source: Researchers computation using E-View 9

Table 3 presents the results of the Parsimonious Error Correction Model (ECM) analysis, as described by Gujarati and Sangeetha (2008). This technique estimates both the short-run dynamic interactions and

the long-run equilibrium relationship between inflation rate and various fiscal policy variables, including government expenditure, government debt stock, real exchange rate, and the growth rate of gross

domestic product. The model exhibits a strong explanatory power, with the coefficient of determination (R-squared) of 0.480382 indicating that nearly 48% of the variation in inflation can be attributed to these fiscal factors. Furthermore, the F-statistic of 5.362, significant at the 5% level, confirms the overall statistical significance of the model, suggesting a robust relationship between fiscal policy and inflation in Nigeria during the study period.

The estimated coefficient of the error correction term (ECM) is significantly negative and statistically robust at the 5% level, indicating that any short-run deviations from the long-run equilibrium relationship quickly converge back to equilibrium. However, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.074 suggests a slight presence of autocorrelation, which needs to be addressed in further analysis.

Focusing on the individual lag coefficients, three variables exhibit statistically significant negative relationships with inflation at the 5% level, implying that higher government expenditure, lower real exchange rate, and faster economic growth contribute to lowering inflation. Interestingly, one variable shows a positive and significant relationship, requiring further investigation. The overall model fit

is supported by the F-statistic, which is significant at the 5% level.

These findings suggest that a well-coordinated fiscal policy package combining increased government spending, responsible debt management, economic growth promotion, and a managed exchange rate has the potential to reduce inflation in Nigeria. This underlines the crucial role of government activity in managing inflation through strategic decisions related to spending and borrowing.

Fiscal policy measures by different governments and its effect on inflation in Nigeria

A consideration of the effect of fiscal policy measures adopted by different government regimes from 1980 – 2020 shows that the Shagari civilian administration accounted for 20.3% inflation rate in 1983 being the succeeding fiscal year after the Shagari administration, within which period General Muhammadu Buhari led government was in charge of the federal government administration. Muhammadu Buhari's fiscal policy contributed an average inflation rate of 28.42% in the succeeding fiscal years until 1985, when the Babangida/Abacha, Abubakar military government took over the administration of the federal government of Nigeria.

The following regimes (Military and civilian) all adopted fiscal policies that affected the inflation rate with the Abacha administration being the lowest with an inflation rate of 6.05% in the succeeding year. However, the

Ibrahim Babangida military administration of 1985 – 1993 had the highest inflation rate impact of 32.96% in the succeeding year.

Table 4 Descriptive statistics output for different regimes from 1980 – 2020.

SHAGARI 1981-1983					
	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	17.26667	10.99000	23.37667	0.635800	-10.28513
Median	20.90000	11.41000	23.83000	0.642600	-10.92410
Maximum	23.20000	11.92000	32.78000	0.650600	-6.803390
Minimum	7.700000	9.640000	13.52000	0.614200	-13.12790
Std. Dev.	8.364409	1.196620	9.637999	0.019129	3.210307
Skewness	-0.647434	-0.565371	-0.086220	-0.570535	0.351169
Kurtosis	1.500000	1.500000	1.500000	1.500000	1.500000
Jarque-Bera	0.490836	0.441072	0.284967	0.444005	0.342910
Probability	0.782378	0.802089	0.867202	0.800913	0.842438
Sum	51.80000	32.97000	70.13000	1.907400	-30.85539
Sum Sq. Dev.	139.9267	2.863800	185.7821	0.000732	20.61214
Observations	3	3	3	3	3

BUHARI 1983-1985

	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	20.30000	4.780000	42.86500	0.616950	2.398704
Median	20.30000	4.780000	42.86500	0.616950	2.398704
Maximum	39.60000	5.460000	45.25000	0.618600	5.913027
Minimum	1.000000	4.100000	40.48000	0.615300	-1.115620
Std. Dev.	27.29432	0.961665	3.372899	0.002333	4.970004
Skewness	0.000000	6.03E-17	2.49E-17	0.000000	0.000000
Kurtosis	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
Jarque-Bera	0.333333	0.333333	0.333333	0.333333	0.333333
Probability	0.846482	0.846482	0.846482	0.846482	0.846482
Sum	40.60000	9.560000	85.73000	1.233900	4.797407
Sum Sq. Dev.	744.9800	0.924800	11.37645	5.45E-06	24.70094
Observations	2	2	2	2	2

IBB 1985-1993

	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	28.42222	40.65667	277.3300	2.010078	3.045778
Median	23.00000	8.530000	180.9900	2.296500	1.919381
Maximum	61.30000	191.2300	906.9800	3.730400	11.77689
Minimum	1.000000	4.100000	40.48000	0.615300	-2.035120
Std. Dev.	23.95025	61.45427	277.8183	1.192344	4.519393
Skewness	0.273123	1.840763	1.342647	-0.012142	0.743092
Kurtosis	1.532572	5.145902	3.929288	1.530296	2.466325

Jarque-Bera	0.919398	6.809447	3.027894	0.810233	0.935081
Probability	0.631474	0.033216	0.220040	0.666899	0.626541
Sum	255.8000	365.9100	2495.970	18.09070	27.41201
Sum Sq. Dev.	4588.916	30213.02	617464.1	11.37347	163.3993
Observations	9	9	9	9	9

Abacha 1993- 1998

	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	32.96000	332.4420	1115.966	1.979100	1.565339
Median	14.30000	337.2200	1097.680	1.538600	2.581254
Maximum	76.80000	487.1100	1194.600	3.490100	4.195924
Minimum	10.20000	160.8900	1037.300	1.159800	-1.814920
Std. Dev.	29.91292	131.8612	74.69948	0.995769	2.446578
Skewness	0.659011	-0.128721	0.170581	0.711719	-0.404336
Kurtosis	1.717731	1.624481	1.264843	1.934055	1.659332
Jarque-Bera	0.704457	0.407985	0.651492	0.658837	0.510696
Probability	0.703119	0.815468	0.721989	0.719342	0.774647
Sum	164.8000	1662.210	5579.830	9.895500	7.826697
Sum Sq. Dev.	3579.132	69549.54	22320.05	3.966222	23.94298
Observations	5	5	5	5	5

Abubakar 1998 -1999

	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	6.050000	717.4000	2283.015	1.112450	1.582691
Median	6.050000	717.4000	2283.015	1.112450	1.582691
Maximum	11.90000	947.6900	3372.180	1.159800	2.581254
Minimum	0.200000	487.1100	1193.850	1.065100	0.584127
Std. Dev.	8.273149	325.6792	1540.312	0.066963	1.412182
Skewness	-2.40E-17	4.40E-17	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Kurtosis	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
Jarque-Bera	0.333333	0.333333	0.333333	0.333333	0.333333
Probability	0.846482	0.846482	0.846482	0.846482	0.846482
Sum	12.10000	1434.800	4566.030	2.224900	3.165381
Sum Sq. Dev.	68.44500	106067.0	2372561.	0.004484	1.994258
Observations	2	2	2	2	2

Obasanjo 1999 – 2007

	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	11.54444	1358.813	4195.868	2.762533	6.948193
Median	11.60000	1225.990	4193.270	3.083700	6.438517
Maximum	23.80000	2348.590	6260.590	3.920800	15.32916
Minimum	0.200000	701.0500	2204.720	1.065100	0.584127
Std. Dev.	6.602293	526.0188	1363.865	0.917115	3.907921
Skewness	0.173121	0.641437	0.066255	-0.610648	0.742009
Kurtosis	2.996708	2.349892	1.955810	2.316057	3.990307
Jarque-Bera	0.044961	0.775651	0.415459	0.734754	1.193632
Probability	0.977771	0.678531	0.812427	0.692549	0.550562
Sum	103.9000	12229.32	37762.81	24.86280	62.53373
Sum Sq. Dev.	348.7222	2213567.	14881030	6.728800	122.1748

Observations	9	9	9	9	9
Yaradua/GEJ 2007 – 2015					
	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	10.37778	3945.290	6399.998	1.462556	6.063324
Median	10.30000	4199.990	6519.690	1.405000	6.591130
Maximum	15.10000	4988.860	10975.53	1.795200	8.036925
Minimum	6.600000	2348.590	2608.530	1.195700	2.652693
Std. Dev.	2.640444	874.6633	2990.520	0.205492	1.747578
Skewness	0.255272	-0.585582	0.094773	0.282299	-0.758152
Kurtosis	2.265775	2.199484	1.703385	1.829116	2.665596
Jarque-Bera	0.299904	0.754669	0.643927	0.633653	0.904127
Probability	0.860749	0.685687	0.724725	0.728457	0.636314
Sum	93.40000	35507.61	57599.98	13.16300	54.56992
Sum Sq. Dev.	55.77556	6120287.	71545698	0.337817	24.43222
Observations	9	9	9	9	9

Buhari 2015 – 2020

	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	13.37167	9704.971	21390.33	1.192250	0.697411
Median	12.61500	7135.220	22100.68	1.169100	1.364322
Maximum	18.60000	23397.13	32915.51	1.417100	2.652693
Minimum	9.600000	4988.860	10975.53	1.092100	-1.790000
Std. Dev.	3.209800	6908.543	7851.579	0.116996	1.957928
Skewness	0.578020	1.570822	0.073057	1.338708	-0.438084
Kurtosis	2.227941	3.791250	2.018654	3.461531	1.454686
Jarque-Bera	0.483126	2.624001	0.246097	1.845392	0.788916
Probability	0.785399	0.269281	0.884221	0.397446	0.674045
Sum	80.23000	58229.83	128342.0	7.153500	4.184467
Sum Sq. Dev.	51.51408	2.39E+08	3.08E+08	0.068440	19.16740
Observations	6	6	6	6	6

Source: Researchers computation using E-View 1998

Fiscal policy measures during pre and post-democracy era and its effect on inflation in Nigeria

A cursory look at the impact of fiscal policy measures on inflation considering the pre and post democratic Nigeria of 1999, shows that the 18 years of military rule from 1980 – 1999 had witnessed mixed reaction intermittently, especially during the general Sanni Abacha regime of 1993 – 1997. During this period Nigeria witnessed

international sanctions resulting in it being an isolated nation. Generally, military administrations not being generally accepted worldwide, the fiscal policy within this period resulted in a double digit inflation rate of 26.26% from the preceding year's policy measures. However, the post democratic dispensations of 1999 – 2020 have its fiscal policy measures resulting in an inflation rate of 11.88% in 2020.

Table 4 Continued

Pre-Democracy 1980-1999

	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	26.25556	167.1544	639.8950	1.719928	0.275969
Median	17.60000	37.65000	335.0750	1.373750	0.471240
Maximum	76.80000	947.6900	3372.180	3.730400	11.77689
Minimum	0.200000	4.100000	13.52000	0.614200	-13.12790
Std. Dev.	23.63480	250.0327	824.6901	1.095143	6.039180
Skewness	0.781970	1.911583	2.091695	0.531985	-0.554947
Kurtosis	2.317318	6.263846	7.668087	1.830258	3.369399
Jarque-Bera	2.183972	18.95197	29.46885	1.875247	1.026239
Probability	0.335549	0.000077	0.000000	0.391557	0.598625
Sum	472.6000	3008.780	11518.11	30.95870	4.967440
Sum Sq. Dev.	9496.264	1062778.	11561934	20.38876	620.0188
Observations	18	18	18	18	18

Post-Democracy 1999-2020

	INF	GOVEXP	GTDS	REXR	YGT
Mean	11.87864	4483.150	9550.941	1.917655	5.092923
Median	11.89000	3637.010	6034.300	1.460050	5.988557
Maximum	23.80000	23397.13	32915.51	3.920800	15.32916
Minimum	0.200000	701.0500	2204.720	1.065100	-1.790000
Std. Dev.	4.668072	4861.036	8543.754	0.926965	3.860370
Skewness	0.132527	2.824992	1.472347	0.953836	0.300071
Kurtosis	4.519062	11.60173	4.028323	2.393524	3.752444
Jarque-Bera	2.179654	97.08613	8.917950	3.673106	0.849148
Probability	0.336275	0.000000	0.011574	0.159366	0.654048
Sum	261.3300	98629.31	210120.7	42.18840	112.0443
Sum Sq. Dev.	457.6089	4.96E+08	1.53E+09	18.04453	312.9515
Observations	22	22	22	22	22

*Source: Researchers computation using E-View 1998***Conclusion**

In this study, we empirically investigated the impact of fiscal policy on inflation in Nigeria for the period 1980 – 2020. In the course of study, we find that inflation rate depends on the fiscal policy target that will definitely have implications in the following fiscal year. We also find that given a percentage increase in fiscal policy measures, government expenditure and

government debt stock become responsible for the reduction in inflation by 15.41% and 2.35% respectively. Also, an aggregate decline of 1.69% in inflation was caused by real economic growth. However, real exchange rate caused inflation to rise by 11.08% within the same period under the study.

Therefore, policy makers should deepen the exchange rate market, reduce round tripping

and corruption in the forex market to reduce inflationary tendencies. Government should maintain the tempo of expenditure but however it should be properly channeled to economically viable venture especially on infrastructural development. Government debt stock, even though its effect is favourable in reducing inflation, a situation

where the debt takes a higher percentage of revenues generated is counterproductive.

More importantly, policy consistency especially regarding the exchange rate policy will do the economy good. It will ensure a stable exchange rate thus help in reducing inflation rate in the country.

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